

COMPARISON OF THE EFFECTS OF MODIFIED 8 TECNIQUE AND THE CLASSICAL REPAIR METHOD ON HEALING IN THE RAT ABDOMINAL HERNIA MODEL

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ABSTRACT. The treatment of hernias varies according to the region, type, and tissue involved. There have been numerous studies on different treatment methods. The objective of this study was to compare the modified 8-suture technique with the standard suture technique in a rat abdominal hernia model. Fourteen adult male albino Wistar rats were used in this study. The animals were randomly assigned to two groups: the control group and the experimental group. Initially, an experimental abdominal hernia was created. The paramedian line was selected as the site for the skin incision. After the skin incision, the subcutaneous connective tissue was removed, and the ventral abdominal muscles were dissected bluntly to create a 3 cm hernia opening. In the control group, simple standard sutures were used for hernia repair. In the study group, the hernial orifice was closed using the modified figure-of-8 technique, followed by simple sutures to close the skin. On postoperative day 21, the animals were euthanized using CO₂. Histopathological analysis revealed that the modified 8-suture technique resulted in less pronounced fibrosis associated with inflammatory changes, decreased areas of necrosis and tissue loss, increased connective tissue around the region, and higher collagen development compared to the standard suture technique. Fibrosis formation was more evident and frequent in the control group with normal sutures, but collagen formation was lower. In conclusion, the data obtained from this study indicate that the modified 8-suture technique provides more effective closure of the hernial ring compared to simple sutures, and the regeneration process is faster than with the standard suture technique. This technique could be considered as an alternative to traditional suture applications for hernias that are large enough to affect the wound line.

Keywords: *Abdominal hernia, modified 8 suture, suturing, rat, wound healing.*

INTRODUCTION

A hernia is characterized by the protrusion of an organ or tissue from its normal anatomical position into a different location, causing swelling [1, 2]. It can be either congenital or acquired [2, 3]. Hernias can occur internally or externally and can be found in various parts of the body, with abdominal hernias being the most common [1, 2, 4]. Factors that contribute to the development of hernias include septic omphalitis, post-surgical complications, obesity, increased abdominal pressure, and trauma [5]. In some cases, hernias can be congenital, occurring when the umbilical opening fails to close a few days after birth [6]. Umbilical hernias are a common hereditary condition in calves

and pigs [6, 7]. Additionally, hernias can develop as a complication of abdominal traumas, birth stress, and previous abdominal surgeries, known as incisional hernias [8, 9].

Hernias have adverse effects on the reproductive health of affected animals and can lead to reduced body weight gain [10]. In pregnant animals, the uterine horn can become trapped in a subcutaneous hernia during the late stage of pregnancy, making vaginal birth difficult [11]. Incarcerated hernias can even result in the death of the patient, depending on the severity and duration of the condition [12]. Mortality rates for incarcerated hernias have been reported as 1.4% after 24 hours, 10% after 24-48 hours, and 21% after 48 hours [13].

The definitive diagnosis of traumatic abdominal hernias involves examining the swelling, identifying the hernial opening, and verifying the retraction of the herniated contents into the abdominal cavity [9]. Unretracted or complicated traumatic abdominal hernias are more challenging to diagnose and must be differentiated from neoplasms, hematomas, cysts, enlarged lymph nodes, and abscesses [9]. Contrast radiography, which involves using barium and performing an X-ray of the patient's digestive system, can be employed to diagnose abdominal hernias [10]. Other imaging techniques such as ultrasound examination or computed tomography (CT) may also be used to confirm the presence of a hernia.

Hernia repair can be achieved through herniorrhaphy, which involves suturing the body tissues, or hernioplasty, which involves implanting foreign materials to reinforce the area. The choice of technique depends on the size of the hernial ring [2]. In cases where the hernial ring is too large, making it impossible to approximate the local tissues without excessive tension, prosthetic implants are utilized. The most commonly used synthetic material is a monofilament plastic mesh made of polypropylene or polyethylene [14]. This material is well-tolerated and not absorbed by wounds [15]. Granulation tissue and capillaries grow through the mesh, forming a strong connective tissue layer within four to six weeks [9]. The mesh should extend 1.5 to 3.0 cm beyond the intact tissue at the sides of the hernial ring and should be attached to strong supporting structures using separate sutures [9]. Early postoperative complications may include pain, seroma formation, and wound infection. Challenges associated with this technique include the possibility of mesh rejection and irritation of adjacent tissue [16].

This study aims to compare the modified 8-suture technique with the standard suture technique for experimentally created abdominal hernias. The modified technique is expected to be faster and more effective in terms of recovery. The study also aims to compare the clinical observations with histopathological examinations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fourteen adult male Albino Wistar rats weighing 250-300 g were used in this study. The study (HADYEK) was conducted after obtaining approval (Decision Number: 2019/23) from the Kırıkkale University Animal Experiments Local Ethics Committee. After the adaptation period of the animals, they were randomly divided into two groups: the control group and the experimental group. An experimental abdominal hernia was created. Before the surgical procedure, the animals were anesthetized with Xylazine hydrochloride (2-5 mg/kg, im) and Ketamine hydrochloride (40-50 mg/kg, im). Meloxicam (Maxicam 5 mg/ml 20ml vial) was administered at a dose of 1 mg/kg subcutan injection for 3 days as a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug for both hernia formation and post-operation pain relief. The paramedian line was selected as the incision

site. The subcutaneous connective tissue was dissected, and a 3 cm hernial ring was created by opening the muscles in the ventral part of the abdomen through blunt dissection. This minimized the risk of reopening the non-ventral incision line (Fig. 1). In all animals, 0/2 PGLA was used as surgical suture material in the hernia line, and 0/2 monofilament non-absorbable polypropylene suture was used for the skin. In the control group, standard simple separate sutures were placed for hernia repair. In the study group, the modified 8 technique was used to close the hernial opening, and the skin was closed with simple separate sutures. The animals were regularly monitored for 21 days. On the 21st postoperative day, the animals were euthanized using CO₂. Tissue samples, including the entire suture line, were collected from the operation area for histopathological examinations.

Fig. 1. Incision line skin and hernia hole. *a:* Paramedian incision line on the skin. *b:* Herniated hole in the median line.

Application of modified 8 suture

After thorough dissection of the hernial opening and its borders, suturing was initiated from the muscle mass to obtain support from the intact muscle group. The needle was inserted into this muscle mass from the outside to the inside, passing through all muscle layers. The other end of the thread was sent parallel to the same line using a different needle. Then, on the opposite side of the hernia opening, the threads were crossed and removed from the solid muscle tissue on the opposite side, from the inside to the outside. A regular knot was made to complete the first stage of suturing. Subsequently, the threads were passed from the outside to the inside of the tissue on the opposite side of the knot, that is, from the tissue opposite the line of the hernia opening, and removed from the skin. The suture was completed with a surgical knot. This method brought the wound edges closer to each other while providing support from the healthy muscle tissue (Fig. 2). One suture on the 3 cm wound line was sufficient with this technique in the rat abdominal hernia model.

Fig. 2. The construction of the modified 8 suture technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

No postoperative complications were observed in any of the animals. During daily clinical examinations, it was noted that wound healing progressed normally in all animals, with no signs such as stagnation, loss of appetite, or pain that would affect their well-being. Mild edematous tissue was observed in the hernia area in animals with modified 8 sutures during the 10-day postoperative period. Naturally, the tissue thickness in the hernia region was higher in animals with modified 8 sutures compared to the control group. The examination performed before euthanization on the 21st postoperative day revealed complete wound healing without hernia recurrence.

During the external examination at the first postmortem control, the gap between the wound edges was wider in the control group, and more prominent scar tissue was observed around it. The wound area had a red crust. The tissue section was thin, and no bleeding areas were found. In the group where the new suture technique was applied, the wound edges were closer to each other and appeared to be fusing. The scar tissue around the wound edges was less prominent and not protruding. However, in some cases, a dark brownish-red tissue crust was observed in the wound area (Figure 3). The tissue section was thicker compared to the control group, and no bleeding areas were found around the sutures.

Fig. 3. Macroscopic findings.

In the control group, the large wound area was covered with partially necrotic tissue, and the sutures were not closed (a). In the experimental group, there was a close junction of the wound lips without exudate, crust, and scarring, achieved with the new suture technique (b). In the control group, the diameter of the wound area narrowed without exudate and scarring due to the new suture technique (c). The diameter of the wound area also narrowed without exudate, crust, and scar in the experimental group, thanks to the new suture technique (d).

Histomorphological evaluation of the peripheral and central muscle sections revealed significant differences in both the transverse and longitudinal sections of the peripheral muscle fibers. In the peripheral region, the striations disappeared in many muscle fibers, and their cytoplasm exhibited a pink homogeneous appearance. Some of the nuclei showed a pyknotic appearance. In the histopathological sections of the suture lines in the study group, the tissue thickness was higher than in the control group. The increased tissue thickness in the modified suture technique was expected since solid tissues provided support (Table 1).

Table 1. Wound diameters in the suture area and tissue thickness at the end of healing.

Sample	Muscle suture (cm)	Cuticular suture (cm)	Total suture thickness (cm)
S1	0.3	0.6	0.9
S2	0.3	0.4	0.9
S3	0.3	0.3	0.6
S4	0.4	0.4	0.5
S5	0.3	0.3	0.5
S6	0.3	0.4	0.5
S7	0.5	0.3	1
C1	0.3	0.3	0.4
C2	0.3	0.3	0.6
C3	0.3	0.3	0.4
C4	0.3	0.3	1
C5	0.3	0.3	0.9
C6	0.3	0.3	0.6
C7	0.3	0.3	0.7

Inflammatory cell infiltrations, consisting of lymphocytes, macrophages, and fewer plasma cells, were observed between muscle bundles in the study group that received the modified 8 suture technique. In one case, it developed into a granulomatous focus with foreign body giant cells, indicating a more severe appearance. Similarly, in the control group, lymphocytes associated with subacute inflammation and inflammatory cell infiltrations containing macrophages, as well as granulomatous focal points around the suture material, were more prominent (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Histopathological changes of transverse and longitudinal sections in the peripheral-central parts of the sutured region of muscle tissue.

Peripheral degenerative-necrotic changes in transverse muscle fibers (arrows), modified 8 suture technique (a1), simple suture technique (a2), x200, H&E.

Peripheral degenerative-necrotic changes in longitudinal muscle fibers (arrows), modified 8 suture technique (b1), simple suture technique (b2), x200, H&E.

Degenerative-necrotic changes (arrows) in transverse muscle fibers in the center, modified 8 suture technique (c1), simple suture technique (c2), x200, H&E.

Degenerative-necrotic changes (arrows) in the longitudinal muscle fibers in the center, modified 8 suture technique (d1), simple suture technique (d2), x200, H&E.

Granulomatous inflammation focus around suture material, modified 8 suture technique (e1), simple suture technique (e2), x100, H&E.

Numerous studies have focused on hernia repair techniques over the years. Various techniques, including suturing, grafts, and synthetic dressings, have been used to repair hernias of different sizes. Despite these advancements, recurrence remains a significant challenge [12, 13, 17, 18, 19]. However, no recurrence was observed in either group in this study. When evaluating the postoperative period, no statistically significant difference was detected in terms of wound healing between the study and control groups.

The appearance of edema in tissues is considered a defensive response of the body and represents the initial stage of the wound healing process, known as the inflammation or lag phase [20]. This stage is characterized by the dilation of blood vessels and increased capillary permeability at the wound site [21]. Rough manipulation of tissues during the separation of the membrane in the hernia opening and hernia sac from the skin creates pressure and edema [21]. In this study, edema was observed at the surgical site during the first week. It was observed that edema in the control group resolved faster than in the

study group. This can be attributed to the modified 8 technique, which involved suturing a thicker tissue layer, leading to increased edema formation. Furthermore, the thickened muscle layer created by the modified suture technique may have contributed to the persistence of edema.

Based on the evaluation data at the end of the study, the wound healing at the hernia line was better in the study group, where the modified 8 suture technique was applied. Although the tissue thickness was higher in the modified suture technique, there was no statistically significant difference in tissue thickness between the two groups at different points in the ventral abdomen where the hernia was created, after the healing process.

According to Moleney, monofilament nylon sutures are significantly superior to other materials [22]. It has been reported that tissues exhibit less tension with nylon sutures compared to silk sutures and that nylon sutures are more effective in promoting fibrous tissue formation. In this study, monofilament non-absorbable polypropylene sutures were used for the skin incision in both groups. The study aimed to evaluate the positive and negative aspects of the suture technique itself, rather than the suture material for the hernia line. Regarding histopathology, it was observed that inflammatory changes, necrotic areas with tissue loss, and fibrosis related to increased connective tissue were less severe in the modified 8 suture technique. Collagen development was more prominent in the modified suture technique, whereas collagenization was observed in only a few cases in the normal suture technique. These findings indicate that the modified suture technique allows for better tissue healing compared to the control group. Additionally, histopathological examinations revealed stronger angiogenesis findings in the study group. This suggests that the modified 8 suture technique does not impede revascularization.

Kanade et al. [23] compared the simple suture technique with the horizontal U suture in calves and reported that the horizontal U suture was more robust in animals with a large hernia opening. However, the edema in the surgical area took longer to resolve compared to the control group. They also found that larger hernia openings required more time for edema resolution and prolonged the recovery period. In the present study, such issues were not encountered in the experimental rat model. Nevertheless, when comparing the suturing techniques, the collagen and fibrous tissue formation in the modified suture technique indicated stronger muscle bonds and more robust sutures than classical techniques.

Non-mesh repairs for large hernias with significant defects can create tension and increase the recurrence rate [24]. In cases where the muscle tissue forming the hernia opening can be approximated, as demonstrated in this study, a strong repair can be achieved without using graft materials by taking support from the intact muscle layer. Similar tension sutures have been recommended, particularly in ruminants [10, 18, 23, 25]. The modified 8 suture technique observed in this study demonstrated that the muscles around the hernia opening overlapped, resulting in stronger adhesion and the formation of a more solid tissue. Considering the postoperative pressures exerted on such an abdominal hernia, especially in animals with higher body weight, this suture technique is expected to be highly beneficial.

CONCLUSION

The data obtained from this study suggest that the new suture technique provides more effective wound closure than conventional sutures and accelerates the regeneration process and tissue remodeling. The modified suture technique can be recommended as an

alternative technique to standard sutures for hernias that extend beyond the wound line. It is anticipated that this technique will yield stronger sutures compared to conventional methods, reducing the risk of recurrence, particularly in the repair of abdominal and umbilical hernias observed in ruminants with higher body weight. Further comprehensive studies involving animals with higher body weights would be beneficial for the development of this technique.

Conflict of Interest. The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

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